

Axonal Conduction Velocity: A Computer Study

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1 Introduction

Much work has been done on the analysis of the wave properties of the action potential as it propagates down an axon [1],[2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], and the nomenclature has become so diverse that some semantic coincidences have spawned inappropriate generalizations. This paper is intended to restore a proper perspective and to derive rigorous statements concerning the propagation velocity.

The paper is structured as follows. In Section 2 we investigate conduction velocity in an axon. We conclude in Section 3. An Appendix provides more details related to the simulations performed.

2 Action Potential Conduction Velocity

Conduction velocity of nerve fibers has long been a subject of intense interest. See for example, the review at the beginning of [14]. In the present paper, we go over the conduction velocity formulation in the context of myelinated nerve fibers required for computer simulation purposes and come to a conclusion as to the best method of computing it from simulation output.

2.1 Preliminaries

We first summarize the physical configuration under study. An axon is a long, slender projection of a nerve cell, or neuron, that conducts electrical impulses away from the neuron's cell body. See Figure 1. It is composed of relatively long sections sheathed in myelin, interrupted by short nodes of Ranvier. Ideally, the axon is straight and cylindrically symmetric and the myelinated sections are longitudinally homogeneous. The electrical impulses are exhibited as voltage drops $V(x, t)$ from the center line of the axon to the external medium, with x measuring distance along the axon and t denoting time.

The voltage $V(x, t)$ satisfies the *cable equation*,

$$C \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} - GV + I \quad (1)$$

where the transversal capacitance C , longitudinal resistance R , and leakage conductance G are uniform (but different) in each of the two regions (myelinated and Ranvier); I denotes any injected current, plus the ion currents generated solely in the nodes of Ranvier in accordance with the Hodgkin-Huxley model [6] (or later variations [2]). The parameters in Equation 1 are per-unit-length.

2.2 Wave Interpretation of Simulation Results

Simulations were obtained by applying the Crank-Nicholson scheme to Equation (1). Numerical details are provided in the appendix.

In Figures 2 through 5 we display simulated voltage profiles at selected times for a 4 cm length of axon with 9 nodes of Ranvier, each having length 2.5×10^{-4} cm and spaced 0.2 cm apart. To eliminate the effect of boundary conditions (Neumann on the left end and Dirichlet on the right end) we stimulated the central node of Ranvier and discontinued the simulation when the boundary voltages became appreciable. Thanks to symmetry, we only need to display the profiles to the right of the central node.

The figures display the stimulated action potential (t_1), spreading out (t_2, t_3, t_4) until it starts to stimulate the adjacent node of Ranvier (t_5), eventually triggering an action potential at that node (t_6). *This* action potential spreads out (t_7, t_8), triggering another action potential at the next downrange node (t_9, t_{10}). And in turn further downrange nodes are triggered. (Note that, in agreement with experiment, the subsequent action potentials only spawn further potentials *downrange*, because the preceding nodes of Ranvier need a recovery time before they can be triggered again.)

Figure 1: Neuron, with a focus on the axon cross-section. The nodes of Ranvier are marked with short red arrows and the myelin sheath with longer red ones.

It is a little misleading to call this propagation a "wave," since the profile does not retain its shape as it propagates down the myelinated segments. However, if we only display the profiles at the instants of triggering, we get the *apparent* wave profiles in Figure 6.

Possibly the misleading Figure 6 has led some investigators to conjecture that the voltage $V(x, t)$ satisfies the *wave equation*

$$\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial t^2} = v^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} \quad (2)$$

whose solutions are superposed shape-invariant functions $V(x, t) = f(x \pm vt)$. Indeed, it has often been proposed to combine Equation (2) with the cable equation, Equation (1), in the hopes of deriving an expression for the propagation velocity v . The futility of this strategy is highlighted by the following observations:

- (i) the only simultaneous solutions of Equation (2) and Equation (1) (with $G = I = 0$) are constant or unbounded:

$$V(x, t) = M + Ne^{RCv(vt-x)} + Pe^{RCv(vt+x)}; \quad (3)$$

- (ii) the graphs of $\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial t^2}$ and $\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2}$ are definitely not proportional (Figure 7).

Indeed, examination of Figures 2 through 5 underscores the difficulty of assigning a "propagation velocity" to the phenomenon. The profiles do not evolve as "waves" within a myelinated segment at all; they resemble more a tidal "swell," or diffusion spreading. In fact the solution of the cable equation (1) with $I = 0$, evolving from an initial delta-function shape, is given by [11]

$$V_{Green}(x, t) = \frac{e^{-Gt/C} e^{-(x-x_0)^2 RC/4t}}{\sqrt{\pi t}} \quad (4)$$

(This is, essentially, the Green's function for the diffusion equation.) Figure 8 displays how closely the profiles of the action potential are tracked by a judiciously scaled replica of the Green's function. For this calculation the nodes of Ranvier have been removed for simplicity.

Figure 2: Simulated action potential, spreading to the right. The x -axis is time and the y -axis is voltage. Here $t_1 < t_2 < t_3 < t_4$.

Figure 3: Simulated action potential, exciting the second node of Ranvier. The x -axis is time and the y -axis is voltage. Here $t_5 < t_6 < t_7 < t_8$.

Figure 4: Simulated action potential, exciting the third node of Ranvier. The x -axis is time and the y -axis is voltage. Here $t_9 < t_{10} < t_{11} < t_{12}$.

Figure 5: Simulated action potential exciting the fourth node of Ranvier and then triggering the fifth node. The x -axis is time and the y -axis is voltage. Here $t_{13} < t_{14} < t_{15} < t_{16}$.

Figure 6: Action potential profiles at triggering instants. Note the equality in the heights of the impulses. The x -axis is time and the y -axis is voltage.

Figure 7: Comparison of spatial and temporal second derivatives of the transmembrane potential, $\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial t^2}$ and $\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2}$. Here the x-axis represents time (upper graph) and position (lower graph). The y-axis represents voltage.

Figure 8: Simulated voltage profiles (black) and Green's function (blue). Note the close overlap between the two curves, in each sub-figure. The progression in time is from the left-most sub-figure to the right-most sub-figure. The x -axes represent time and the y -axes voltage.

2.3 The Conduction Velocity

Since the voltage profiles only occasionally appear as shifted replicas of themselves, it would appear that the wisest strategy for assigning a conduction velocity v to the spreading of the action potential is suggested by Figure 6; we take v to be the ratio of the distance L between two consecutive Ranvier nodes, divided by the time lapse τ between the triggering of action potentials at the nodes.

The distance L , of course, is well defined. To demonstrate the *feasibility* of specifying the time lapse τ , let us assume for the moment that the birth of an action potential at a node of Ranvier occurs when the voltage at that node $V(x, t)$ achieves a critical value V_c . And we assume that the action potential is well approximated by a scaled version of the Green's function, Equation (4). Then the triggering event is described by the equation

$$V_{Green}(\tau) = \frac{K e^{-G\tau/C} e^{-L^2 RC/4\tau}}{\sqrt{\pi\tau}} = V_c. \quad (5)$$

and the velocity is given formally by

$$v = \frac{L}{\tau} = \frac{L}{V_{Green}^{-1}(V_c)} \quad (6)$$

A plot of $V_{Green}(\tau)$ versus τ demonstrates that Equation (5) produces a well-defined time lapse τ , Figure 9.

Obviously (5) does not predict a constant $\frac{L}{\tau}$ ratio; the conduction velocity varies with the myelin segment length L .

But the point is made: a triggering condition based on voltage $V(L, \tau) = V_c$, on longitudinal current $I_l(L, \tau) = -\frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial V(L, \tau)}{\partial x} = I_c$, or on charge accumulation $Q = \int_0^\tau I(L, t) dt = Q_c$ [15] specifies a well-defined time lapse τ and thus a conduction velocity. But this computation need not be based on crude approximations like (5) (which makes no attempt to allow for different values of the electric parameters in the nodes of Ranvier); it can be gleaned from simulations. One can visually identify the times at which the action potential spikes peak, and deduce τ by subtraction.

2.4 Observations

1. For a given internode distance L , the time lapse between every consecutive pair of action potential triggerings appears to be the same.
2. However, the velocity v does vary with internode distance L , apparently possessing a maximum. See Figure 10, compiled from simulations.
3. Which parameter (V , I , or Q) triggers the action potential when it (the parameter) achieves a critical value? Some authors suggest it is accumulated charge Q (which may be equivalent to voltage, through capacitance). Action potential initiation is very difficult to detect precisely from simulations, because once an action potential has been initiated it dominates, and thus distorts, the voltage profile. Also there is the issue of where the

Figure 9: Plot of the Green's function with respect to the second argument, $V_{Green}(L, \tau)$ versus τ . The critical value of transmembrane voltage at which an action potential is triggered is indicated on the y -axis, as V_C .

Figure 10: Plot of the conduction velocity of an action potential, versus internode length.

parameter should be measured. We circumvented the issue of *when* the action potential is triggered by simply noting the instants of peak voltage.

3 Conclusion

Specialists recognize that the cable equation is of the parabolic type (diffusive), and not hyperbolic (wave). The propagation between nodes of Ranvier is more of a surge than a wave. The “chain reaction” nature of the action potentials is only suggestive, and does not justify attributing any of the features of the wave equation to the phenomenon. By discussing these features rigorously, we hope to have illuminated them in a way that is useful to computational neuroscientists and mathematicians alike.

Appendix: Details of the Simulations

The simulations were obtained by applying the Crank-Nicolson scheme to the cable equation simplified with an integrating factor,

$$\frac{\partial[e^{Gt/CV}]}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{RC} \frac{\partial^2[e^{Gt/CV}]}{\partial x^2} + \frac{e^{Gt/CI}}{C} \quad (7)$$

Table 1: Nomenclature for Section 2

Symbol	Meaning	Values (with references)
d	diameter	1e-3 cm [12]
x	position in centimeters	
t, τ, t_1, \dots	time in seconds	
C_{myelin}, C	myelin sheath's capacitance per unit length	1.87e-11 F/cm [[9],[12]]
$C_{Ranvier}$	nodal capacitance per unit length	3.14e-9 F/cm [12]
$R_{myelin}, R_{Ranvier}, R$	resistance per unit length at the node and myelin	1.27e8 Ohm/cm [12]
G_{myelin}, G	conductance per unit length at the myelin	5.6e-9 per Ohm-cm [[9],[12]]
$G_{Ranvier}$	conductance per unit length at the node	0
I	injected current; details in text	$-4 \times 10^{-5} \frac{A}{cm}$
$\delta x, \delta t$	mesh size	0.02 cm, $2 \times 10^{-6} s$
$m, n, h, p; y$	activation/inactivation variables, and stand-in variable	
α, β	activation/inactivation coefficients	
v	conduction velocity	
V, V_{Green}, V_c	voltage	
K, M, N, P	general solution coefficients	
L	node of Ranvier spacing	
Q, Q_c	charge	

employing mesh sizes $\delta x = 0.02$ cms, $\delta t = 2e - 6$ seconds (and confirmed with $\delta x = 0.04$ cm, $\delta t = 8e - 6$ seconds). Overall dimensions and boundary conditions are described in what follows.

Values used in the simulations reported in this section are shown in Table 1.

The injected current was -4×10^{-5} A/cm for a duration of 4×10^{-6} seconds. No leakage current was presumed at the nodes of Ranvier. The sodium, potassium and ‘‘nonspecific’’ (p) ion currents at these nodes are expressed in terms of Hodgkin-Huxley activation/inactivation variables m, n, h and p (which are dimensionless) as follows: $j_{Na} = \pi d P_{Na} m^2 h Z(Na)$, $j_K = \pi d P_K n^2 Z(K)$, $j_p = \pi d P_p p^2 Z(p)$ A/cm, where, with $Y = Na, K$,

$$Z(Y) = \frac{F^2(V - 0.07)}{RT} \times \frac{[Y]_0 - [Y]_i e^{F(V-0.07)/RT}}{e^{F(V-0.07)/RT} - 1}$$

in units of Coulombs/cubic centimeter. Here the resting potential is -0.07 volts, T is the absolute temperature ($25 + 273.15$ K), F is the Faraday constant (96,485 Coulombs/mole), and R is the gas constant (8.3145 J/K-mole). P_{Na}, P_K, P_p denote the permeabilities. The outer and inner concentrations are taken as $[Na]_o = 1.145 \times 10^{-4}$, $[Na]_i = 1.374 \times 10^{-5}$, $[K]_o = 2.5 \times 10^{-6}$, $[K]_i = 1.2 \times 10^{-4}$ moles/cm³. The activation/inactivation variables each satisfy [[6],[2]]

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = [\alpha_y(1 - y) - \beta_y y] Q(T) \quad (8)$$

where $y = (m, n, h, p)$. Here $Q(T)$ is a temperature factor (with $T = 298.15$ K) and the coefficients (α_y, β_y) are voltage-dependent [$V = V(x, t)$] functions whose tabulations have persistently been reported with incorrect dimensions in the literature, even in some of the references cited in this paper. In our simulations we used

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_h &= \frac{A_*(B_* - V)}{1 - e^{(V - B_*)/C_*}}, \beta_h = \frac{A_*}{1 + e^{(B_* - V)/C_*}}, \\ \alpha_y &= \frac{A_*(V - B_*)}{1 - e^{(B_* - V)/C_*}}, \beta_y = \frac{A_*(B_* - V)}{1 - e^{(V - B_*)/C_*}}, y = m, n, p; \\ A_{\alpha_h} &= 1e5, A_{\alpha_m} = 3.6e5, A_{\alpha_n} = 2e4, A_{\alpha_p} = 6e3 \text{ per volt-s} \\ A_{\beta_h} &= 4.5e3 \text{ per s} \\ A_{\beta_m} &= 4e5, A_{\beta_n} = 5e4, A_{\beta_p} = 9e4 \text{ per volt-s} \\ B_{\alpha_n} &= -1e - 2, B_{\alpha_m} = 2.2e - 2, B_{\alpha_n} = 3.5e - 2, B_{\alpha_p} = 4e - 2 \text{ volts} \\ B_{\beta_h} &= 4.5e - 2, B_{\beta_m} = 1.3e - 2, B_{\beta_n} = 1e - 2, B_{\beta_p} = -2.5e - 2 \text{ volts} \\ C_{\alpha_h} &= 6e - 3, C_{\alpha_m} = 3e - 3, C_{\alpha_n} = 1e - 2, C_{\alpha_p} = 1e - 2 \text{ volts} \\ C_{\beta_h} &= 1e - 2, C_{\beta_m} = 2e - 2, C_{\beta_n} = 1e - 2, C_{\beta_p} = 2e - 2 \text{ volts.} \end{aligned}$$

We adopted values for the permeabilities from [2] as follows: $P_{Na} = 8e - 3$ cm/s, $P_p = 0.54e - 3$ cm/s, $P_K = 1.2e - 3$ cm/s. If we regard $V(x, t)$ as constant over time intervals of length δt , the coefficients in Equation (8) are also constant and its solutions satisfy:

$$y(t + \delta t) = y(t)e^{-(\alpha_y + \beta_y)Q\delta t} + (1 - e^{-(\alpha_y + \beta_y)Q\delta t})\frac{\alpha_y}{\alpha_y + \beta_y}; \quad (9)$$

this formula is used in the simulations.

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